

WORKING WITH NEWSPAPER MATERIAL IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS**Ergasheva Nilufar**

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Abstract. *The article considers the methods of using newspaper materials in Russian language lessons, in secondary schools, noted the relevance of reading newspapers for the moral development of young people.*

Keywords: *newspaper material, newspaper "Jizzakh Truth," children's journalism.*

РАБОТА С ГАЗЕТНЫМ МАТЕРИАЛОМ НА УРОКАХ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются методы использования газетных материалов на уроках русского языка, в общеобразовательных школах, отмечается актуальность чтения газет для нравственного развития молодежи.*

Ключевые слова: *газетный материал, газета «Джизакская правда», детская журналистика.*

INTRODUCTION

Speech is one of the types of communication. It enriches a person, serves as a subject of art. Insufficient command of speech is an objective reason that makes it impossible to freely participate in the life of modern society. The problem of developed speech is especially important today, when the importance of the correct persuasive word is growing.

When live communication of students is limited to various gadgets. For children, developed speech is the key to successful learning and development. Enrichment of vocabulary is a sign of high human development.

Teaching speech creativity is teaching children the ability to speak and write in the process of creating texts of different styles and genres.

The actual task of forming the speech culture of the personality of the younger generation is successfully solved today by journalism, which corresponds to the social order of society and the growing generation.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The educational potential of these printed publications is wide: they introduce teenagers to the intellectual and spiritual potential of society, serve as an important channel for transmitting information from the older generation to the younger, and at the same time - a means of communication that allows the young audience to communicate with each other and learn about the world. Consequently, the media today are considered as one of the factors contributing to the speech and cultural development of the individual

The secondary school is faced with the task of not only teaching, but also educating future specialists, shaping their worldview and moral qualities. Regular use of the newspaper can play an indispensable role in Russian language lessons in solving both general educational and educational tasks. This will provide an opportunity to diversify the forms of work that contribute to the development of the educational process, expand the potential vocabulary of students through the most important, frequent vocabulary, improve the speech skills and abilities

necessary for communication in the socio-political, socio-cultural communicative spheres, consolidate individual skills of the student and familiarization reading, etc.

The modern information society sets new tasks for education: “not to teach” for life, but to teach to learn for life. Instead of accumulating knowledge, it is necessary today to focus students on the development of the ability to acquire knowledge and the formation of the ability to use the acquired knowledge and the formation of the ability to use the acquired knowledge in practice. Such educational results cannot be achieved using only traditional pedagogical technologies, more precisely, central educational resources, The future starts today. Spiritual and moral purity, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness, etc. do not come by themselves. Education is at the core of everything. Yes, the role of children's journalism in this matter is very large. Like newspapers for adults, children's journalism poses important educational tasks depending on the age and level of development of children. Any work or article written for children should be understandable and interesting, as well as correspond to their age characteristics. Children's journalism is closely connected with pedagogy. The goal and task of both directions is the same: to give the younger generation a real mental, moral, aesthetic education and to educate worthy children of our time from it.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The possibilities of the press are enormous: the newspaper is a messenger of information about social life, a means of communication between students, teachers and parents, promotes the development of students' creative abilities and is one of the ways of self-expression and self-realization.

Each school is a small state with its own laws, traditions and course of life. Each such state is unique in its own way. The main task of the newspaper is to be able to tell about this life in such a way that the headings are of interest to all segments of the population.

In the Russian language lessons, newspapers and magazines are one of the means of carrying out educational tasks. For example, we can take the newspaper "Jizzakh Truth". It highlights various general educational, cultural, socio-economic, political headings of Uzbekistan.

For example, it highlights such headings as: "Edges of education", "Health", "Mass sports", "Book-beacon of education", etc.

Influencing the emotions and mind of the reader, the articles of this newspaper contribute to the generation in students of the desire to live with dignity, to earn the respect of others, awakening creative energy and strength. For example: No. 17.2022, under the heading "Edges of Education", an article was published under the title, "Why am I learning Russian?". Here the author talks about his experience of learning the Russian language, and notes how important it is to learn Russian for the growing generation. Based on this article, it seemed to me that the greatness, richness and euphony of the Russian language is the subject of admiration for many people.

Collaboration with the newspaper helps the children to increase their vocabulary, when writing essays to build sentences correctly, to express their thoughts more accurately, and to improve their reading technique. All this becomes the key to improving academic performance.

Reading journalistic articles in the Russian language lessons educates and develops the cognitive abilities of students. It teaches them to notice the distinguishing features of the study of various spheres, typical social phenomena of social life and give them a reasonable assessment.

Helping children to master the art of speech is the main thing in the activities of the newspaper. Do not constrain the speech of children, preserve their living word, support the desire of children for self-expression through verbal creativity, develop their innate gift for words. It is necessary to provide children with the opportunity to speak and write freely - about what they would like, what excites them, interests them, speak and write sincerely, with the confidence that they will be understood. And for this it is necessary that there be an atmosphere of mutual common interest in each other, an atmosphere of trust. We ourselves create this atmosphere for children.

CONCLUSION

The newspaper helps to identify the best qualities of a person, form moral priorities, and prepare students for choosing further goals in learning. In addition, there is an improvement in the ability to clearly, logically, competently express one's thoughts. Reading articles gives aesthetic pleasure, pleases meeting with the extraordinary in life, reveals the richness and beauty of the language being studied. Reading periodicals is of great educational importance for students.

Literature:

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